

Multivocal Literature Review Protocol

Search String

((platform) AND (sided OR digital OR business OR product OR ecosystem OR market))

Search Engine

Google Search Engine

Period of the Search

The search covered the period from 2016 to 2020

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria	Description
IC1	URL works (the content is available via the URL).
IC2	Indicate strategies that support the creation and maintenance of ecosystems.
EC1	If the webpage is only videos, audio, or images without text, it should be excluded.
EC2	Article from Quora, Slideshare, or LinkedIn, because on Quora and LinkedIn the discussion happens without a detailed reflection. Similarly, Slideshare provides presentation material on several subjects but also lacks detailed reflection.

Academic Studies (S1 - S23) and Gray Literature (G1 - G23) Included in the Multivocal Literature Review

[S1] Angeren, J. V.; Kabbedijk, J.; Jansen, S.; Popp, K.M. A survey of associate models used within large software ecosystems. In: Proceedings of the Third Workshop on Software Ecosystems, Springer, 2011.

[S2] Ceccagnoli, M.; Forman, C.; Huang, P.; Wu, D. J. Cocreation of value in a platform ecosystem: the case of enterprise software, MIS Quarter, 2012, 36(1), 263–290.

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- [S11] Avila, A.; Terzidis, O. Management of partner ecosystems in the enterprise software industry. In: 8th International Workshop on Software Ecosystem, Dublin, Ireland, 10 December 2016.
- [S12] Angeren, J. v.; Blijleven, V.; Jansen, S. Relationship intimacy in software ecosystems: A survey of the Dutch software industry. In: Proceedings of the International Conference on Management of Emergent Digital EcoSystems, ACM, November, 2011. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2077489.2077502>.
- [S13] Huang, P.; Ceccagnoli, M.; Forman, C.; Wu, D. J. Appropriability mechanisms and the platform partnership decision: Evidence from enterprise software, ManagScien, 2013, 59 (1), 102–121. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.1120.1618>.
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